

PHILOSOPHY AND ETHICS

ON THE ONTOLOGICAL SOURCES OF NON-LINEARITY IN POETIC SYNERGETICS

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Abstract

This article is devoted to studying the ontological problems of non-linearity within the framework of poetic synergetics. It interprets the irregularity in time and space in the evolution of a living organism with reference to the scientific and philosophical foundations of P.K.Anokhin's functional system theory and the non-linearity of cognitive processes according to the principles of preventive reflection set out by P.K.Anokhin and the principles of isomorphism to reality set out by H. Follmer.

Non-linearity in the poetic system is formed as a result of the correspondence between poetic thinking and the surrounding world's non-linearity, as well as between poetic language and poetic thinking. The main sources of non-linearity are the multivariance between the content and expression plans, the hierarchical structural heterogeneity of poetic forms, and the complexity and branching of plots, metaphors and concepts.

Keywords: poetic synergetics, nonlinearity, isomorphism, attractor, phase portrait

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Poetry is defined as the art of words, and it has had a significant impact on the development and enrichment of human culture. Poetic expression has long been considered the purview of the sacred; the manner in which individuals approach nature, society, joy, sorrow, and the most profound desires were initially articulated through poetic mediums.

Nizami's literary works addressed the function of words in human existence.

Biz öz nəzərimizi sözə bağlamışiq,
Bizi öldürən də, (əbədi) diri saxlayan da odur [2, s. 51].
(We have fixed our gaze on the word,
It is the word who kills us and keeps us alive (forever))

The harmonious human personality is primarily formed by the art of poetry, enriching its spiritual world.

Poetry has been demonstrated to serve as a means of comprehending the world in which we reside. The processes occurring in the surrounding reality are predominantly non-linear, and non-linearity constitutes the ontological basis of reality. The non-linear mode of thinking is the result of the evolution of Homo sapiens as a biosociological being.

The epistemology of evolution is of methodological importance when conducting a comparative analysis between the evolution of a living organism and the system of poetry.

Evolutionary processes are characterised by non-linearity, complexity and multi-stage progression. The intricacies of the laws of evolution of living organisms are elucidated in the functional system theory of P.K. Anokhin.

P.Anokhin's concept of systemogenesis is founded upon three principles. The following principles are to be considered: 1) The principle of heterochrony, defined as the selectivity and speed of maturation of the morphological basis of a functional system; 2) The principle of combining elements into a single functional system; 3) The principle of minimum provision of functions. Consequently, the fundamental process of systemogenesis can be defined as "a series of embryonic processes that selectively open the way to system connections with the regularities of morphogenetic maturation of individual structural elements" [3, 136]. The development of body parts occurs at different times and at different speeds, depending on the priority of the functions they carry. Selective systemic connections are defined as various structural units adapted and accelerated in localization, which corresponds to the mechanism of the resonance effect of synergism. P.K. Anokhin's concept of anticipatory decline justifies the adaptation of human thinking to environmental changes since ancient times.

H.Follmer identifies isolation as the principal factor in the evolution of cognitive processes. The central tenet of his theory is the concept of "isomorphism", which he posits as the predominant characteristic of cognitive processes. "The fact of adaptation is a minimum condition for cognition. The subjective structures of cognition adapt to the world, because they were formed in the course of evolution, adapting to this world" [11, pp.43-48]. It is evident that, as a consequence of prolonged evolutionary processes, human cognition adapts to the non-linearity inherent in the relationship and interaction between objects in the world around us. Consequently, structural and functional morphism is formed between cognitive methods and reality. Non-linearity, that is, multivariate, leaps become the main attributes of thinking.

It is evident that since the late XX century novel scientific methodologies have been systematically employed in the domain of humanitarian research. This, in turn, gives rise to the question of establishing a shared language between the social sciences and the natural sciences. Gaston Bachelard provides a detailed discussion of this subject. "Science truly gives rise to philosophy. Furthermore, philosophy must also be capable of adapting its language to convey modern thought in its dynamics and originality" [4, p.29]. The establishment of each new discovery in the field of natural science provides a novel approach and perspective on the understanding of natural phenomena. A novel

scientific-philosophical interpretation of natural phenomena is presented in the appropriate philosophical lexicon, through terminological units. If necessary, it is important to find a new term. This constitutes the fundamental principle of the "adaptation of philosophical language". The concept of synergetics incorporates this "adaptation" function.

Non-linearity in synergetic systems manifests itself in diverse forms within the domain of poetry.

The relationship between the evolution of living organisms and the evolution of Azerbaijani folk poetry has been studied in the context of P. K. Anokhin's functional systems theory [7].

Non-linearity, as a complex phenomenon, has been demonstrated to exist in both the material world and the spiritual realm of human experience. Consequently, when studying non-linearity, it is necessary to take into account various factors: The following three points are to be considered: 1) The specificity of non-linearity in the material and spiritual worlds; 2) Methods of transformation of the main properties of non-linearity from the material world to the mental world; 3) Features of the transformation of non-linear thought into verbal, especially poetic expressions. In the process of transformation of reflex into thought and verbal expression, the properties of heterogeneity and non-linearity acquire new qualities. Furthermore, poetic thought and speech represent special phenomena, the study of which necessitates consideration of these features.

Essentially, poetic reflection is a poetic form of perception of reality, a method of intuitive-rational, figurative-analytical reflection of the external world, and at the same time, a search for new methods of cognition, an assessment of theoretical and practical views on the meaning of creativity, the purpose of the poet and poetry.

Poetic thought, as a systemic-syncretic and multicomponent phenomenon, is based on "the problem of analogy of being with all its uncertainty and uniqueness - the problem of metaphor as a whole" [9, p. 787]. Poetic thought is characterised by the incompleteness of the idea, or "metaphoricality", which implies mental procedures beyond rationality (i.e. intuitive, figurative, etc.).

V.V.Nalimov's work explores the non-linear characteristics of ordinary spoken language. As posited by Bally, it appears that he was the first linguist to draw attention to one feature of everyday human language: its non-linearity, which is conditioned by the two-dimensionality of the sign system (p. 61). The author draws attention to the non-linearity of poetic language, as well as its integrity and structural flexibility. The organisation of the poetic text is such that the words are not limited by each other, but rather, the meanings of the words are expanded, and they merge into a smooth and unified stream [8, p. 241]. The elasticity, flexibility and variability of the internal form of the word are determined by the flexibility of thought. According to Sapir, the definition of the word is as follows: "the thought that encompasses thousands of different phenomena of experience and can encompass thousands more" [10, p.35].

The transformation of categories of thought into categories of language and vice versa is a complex, nonlinear and multi-stage process. The progression of thought is theorised as an internal movement through a series of planes. The transformation of thought into language, and subsequently back into thought, is a recurrent theme in this theoretical framework [5, p.305].

Language and thinking represent two complementary aspects of social activity, and the relationship between them is dynamic, reflecting the result of evolution: "the relationship between thought and word emerges, evolves and flourishes over the course of a protracted period of cognitive and linguistic development" [6, s.279].

The preceding discussion demonstrates how the heterogeneity in the structure of the reflex and the non-linearity of the form of activity are transformed into the philosophical definition and poetic expression of thought.

The law of irregularity in space-time in evolutionary processes

constitutes the primary source for the scientific and philosophical interpretation of the dynamics of the interaction and relations between the elements of objects and processes. The ontological basis of non-linearity is therefore said to be irregularity in space and time. Spatial irregularity is attributed to the heterogeneity of the constituent elements of complex systems and the relative independence of elements in the development process. In a broader sense, spatial irregularity is explained by the difference in the transformation speeds of elements in the transformation of an entire system or concept into another system or concept. Temporal irregularity is attributed to the different speeds of development in different time periods.

In the poetic text, this irregularity is manifest in the uneven distribution of semantic density throughout the composition.

The primary notion of the poem can be identified in any stanza or line. This phenomenon can be attributed to the spontaneous genesis of poetry, which only becomes discernible after its completion. The manner in which meaning is loaded within a poem, and the metaphors, concepts and phraseological units through which it is conveyed, can only be ascertained once the poem has been fully realised.

In the domain of poetry, the word is capable of expanding its semantic field beyond its lexical meaning, thereby unveiling hitherto unexplored shades of meaning. Moreover, it is employed to articulate that which is inherently indescribable. The poetic language is characterised by a richness in metaphors, which endow the native language with a flexible structure. The principle of analogy of metaphor facilitates the expression of "the greater in the smaller".

The presence of multiple expression plans within the content plan is one of the factors that engender non-linearity. Multivariance constitutes a prerequisite for non-linearity. The inherent nature of this subject is such that a parallel can be drawn with the well-known inverse problem that is prevalent in the field of mathematics. The inverse problem is multivariant and constructive. The resolution of such problems engenders creativity and imagination. The multivariance of the expression plan is a significant source of creativity in the domain of poetry, leading to the emergence of new works and artists. In order to provide an explanation for this phenomenon, an analysis is required that considers the influence of Nizami on the creativity of oriental poets. The corpus of Nizami's "Khamsa" comprises more than 600 verses. Amongst Nizami's followers, we can mention such eminent poets as Amir Khosrov Dehlavi, Amir Alisher Navai, Abdurrahman Jami, and Mahammad Fuzuli.

Amir Khosrov Dehlavi dedicated five poems, comprising approximately 20,000 verses in total, to Nizami's Khamsa. In addition to his prodigious poetic output, he has also published extensively on prose, musicology and scientific subjects. A significant proportion of his scientific oeuvre pertains to the scientific principles of poetry.

The renowned Uzbek poet, philosopher, and eminent statesman Amir Alisher Navai composed five masnavis in Turkish for the first time as a response to Nizami's Khamsa. Alisher Navai's creation exerted a profound influence on the literary traditions of Turkic-speaking communities. The eminent Tajik poet, musicologist, philosopher, and scholar Abdurrahman Jami composed the masnavi "Leyli and Majnun" under the influence of Nizami's work of the same name. The renowned Azerbaijani poet, Mahammad Fuzuli, is widely regarded as having created one of the most enduring love epics in world literature with his magnum opus, "Leyli and Majnun". The examples presented demonstrate that the multivariate between the content plan and the expression plan is indicative not only of non-linearity, but also a factor that plays a fundamental role in the development of great artists and the creation of poetry schools.

The issue of non-linearity in poetry can be elucidated by examining tajnis, a particular poetic form of Turkish folk poetry.

The rhymes and parallels of the tajnis consist of cinas. Cinas

are words or word combinations that are close to each other in structure or pronunciation, but different in content. They are formed by the principle of paradigmatics. From this point of view, cinas systems are non-linear.

Each stanza of the cighali tajnis (a type of poetic form based on the couplet pattern, but with a cighali bayati added after the second line of each stanza) is formed from the synthesis of a seven-syllable bayati tajnis and an eleven-syllable tajnis. The bayati tajnis occupies a central position within the tajnis and is characterised by its nuclear function. This observation suggests that the tajnis can be regarded as a poetic form with a planetary structure. Given that the structure of the tajnis and bayati tajnis is non-linear, a double non-linearity is obtained as a result of synthesising these two poetic forms.

Metaphor has been identified as a primary source of non-linearity. The nature of poetic thought and its form of expression, that is to say, poetic language, is metaphorical by its very essence. Humans acquire knowledge about unfamiliar objects through familiar ones. The process of comparison is utilised to discern the unfamiliar from the familiar, while the identification of analogies serves as a fundamental component in the evaluation of novel entities. Metaphor is defined as the formation of connections between material and spiritual objects of differing natures and scales. It is characterised by heterogeneity in structure and serves as a form of expression that represents the internal unity of the world. The utilisation of metaphor has been a recurrent theme in the creation of natural scientists, philosophers and poets, particularly in their endeavours to comprehend the intricacies of the surrounding world. Concomitantly, it would be judicious to recollect the primacy of poetic thinking and poetic language, the fact that they are primary. The structural analogy of poetic thinking to reality was established through the utilisation of metaphor as a consequence of evolutionary processes. The preceding discussion indicates that non-linearity is an inherent, ontological attribute of poetry.

Günahkar kimsəne nara hey yanar,
Nə kövsəri görər, nə sağı bilər [1, s.54].
(A sinful soul forever burns in the fire;

It sees no Kawthar, nor knows the path of salvation)

The philosophical substance of the verse comprises an exposition of a universal dilemma: by leading a sinless existence in this world and engaging in virtuous deeds, an individual attains happiness both in reality and in the afterlife. However, those who perpetrate grave sins will encounter substantial retribution in both this life and the hereafter.

In these verses, parallels are drawn in a laconic form between a happy life lived in the real world and happiness in the afterlife. The pinnacle of human flourishing is the pursuit of beneficial actions for the betterment of society, the nurturing of future generations, the witnessing of the matrimonial union of one's progeny, the maintenance of their well-being, and the attainment of esteem from one's peers. The happiness of those who perform good deeds is believed to extend to the afterlife, where they are thought to be destined to witness the Kowsar in paradise and to partake of its water, which is said to be whiter than snow and sweeter than honey.

The verse delineates a bifurcation point, and a phase portrait can be constructed in accordance with the content of the verse (Figure 1.).

The F axis is representative of the degree of punishment, whilst the M axis is indicative of the regularity parameter, which is an indicator of sins in human behaviour. As illustrated in Figure 1, Mk denotes the point of bifurcation. Should the transgressions committed by human beings exceed this limit, they are subject to severe retribution in both this life and the hereafter. At the point of bifurcation, the developmental trajectories of the system are exhibited in the form of a "fork".

Figure 1. The relationship between people's sins and their punishments

Within the domain of poetry, a dual reflection of reality transpires, manifesting in the form of poetic thought and poetic language. The reflection in thought undergoes a transformation into a verbal form, with the process itself being founded upon a sequence of nonlinear transformations.

The manifestation of heterogeneity can be observed in various forms, including the unity between the material and the ideal in the reflex, the principle of non-linearity in poetic thought, and the poem itself as a semiotic system.

Due to their hierarchical structure, the ramifications in the plots of epic poems are more complex than the attractor chains that exist in the development process of synergetic systems.

The evolution of complex processes is studied in synergetic using strict mathematical models. Poetic synergetic employs verbal models to analyse and articulate these processes. Verbal models are characterised by their flexibility and universality, which arise from the inexhaustible possibilities of the art of speech. The tendency of poetic language and thinking towards the transcendent, the structural-functional analogy to the non-linearity of the material and spiritual world, the expression of the "inexpressible", the adequate description of life's events and the poetic understanding of them have additional cognitive and lexical possibilities.

The "carriers" of non-linearity are metaphors, aphorisms and ethnocultural concepts that express non-linear life situations and cognitive operations.

The poetic system is characterised by greater mobility and adaptability in comparison with biological and technical systems.

Synergistic categories in poetry are subject to constant change, with new content and forms of embodiment emerging over time.

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